

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Opportunities for Carbon Dioxide Removal from European pulp and paper plants

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

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Abstract
<p>This report presents estimations of potential quantities and associated costs for Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) via bio-CCS from European pulp and paper plants with biogenic emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. By setting the cut-off criteria at 250 kt/a of biogenic CO₂, 58 of the 856 European pulp and paper mills are included in the analysis. Although this is a small share of the total number of mills, the selection covers all large biogenic emitters in the sector, including primarily kraft pulp producers. Most of the excluded mills produce paper and/or board with no integrated pulp production, and some are mechanical pulp/paper or recycled pulp producers. The majority of the excluded mills have very low or no biogenic CO₂ emissions.</p> <p>For the selected mills, the report presents geographically resolved potentials for bio-CCS, along with costs for CO₂ capture, conditioning and transportation to a sub-sea permanent storage site in the North Sea region, considering the AMP/PZ amine-based capture technology. In order to reduce operating costs for the capture plant, it is important to maximize heat integration with the mill. The</p>

analysis presented explores different heat integration scenarios based on learnings from previous work performed in Work Package 5 of the ACCESS project. The **Reference scenario** assumes that a stand-alone biomass boiler is used to cover the additional heat demand imposed by the CO₂ capture process. This scenario establishes a baseline for the cost and additional biomass demand that would result from a large-scale implementation of bio-CCS in European pulp and paper mills. The **Minimized fuel use scenario** assumes that low-pressure steam to supply the heat demand for CO₂ capture is supplied by bypassing the mill's steam turbines, i.e., sacrificing electricity production to drive the capture process.

The estimation of biogenic CO₂ emissions (which constitutes the theoretical CDR potential, assuming that it is possible to capture most of the biogenic CO₂ emissions from pulp and paper mills) from the European pulp and paper sector indicates that the potential for CDR is located mainly in large pulp and paper mills in Sweden and Finland, where there is an active forestry industry and a large prevalence of kraft pulp mills. In total, the biogenic emissions from the mills included in the analysis are around 55 MtCO₂/a. The EU Industrial Carbon Management Strategy outlines targets based on modelling results that indicate levels of CO₂ capture of around 280 and 450 Mt/a in 2040 and 2050 respectively. In 2040, almost half of the captured CO₂ would have to come from biogenic sources or the atmosphere, increasing towards 2050. With biogenic emissions of around 55 MtCO₂/a, the pulp and paper industry could in theory be a major contributor in reaching these targets. Kraft pulp mills make up most of the biogenic emissions from the sector, i.e. 49 out of the 58 mills covered in the analysis, contributing 48 out of the 55 MtCO₂/a. Assuming a CO₂ capture rate of 90% it is concluded that around 50 MtCO₂/a of biogenic CO₂ could be captured.

The results presented in this report show clearly that the costs for CDR from European pulp and paper mills, and the cost-optimal strategy for supplying the heat necessary for the CO₂ separation, are highly context dependent. The estimated costs span a wide range, between 85-534 €/tCO₂ avoided, depending both on the size and location of the individual mill, as well as on the assumptions applied regarding the maturity of the capture technology, available transportation modes, energy prices, and heat integration scenario. Furthermore, the electricity price and grid carbon intensity have a large impact on the cost optimal heat supply strategy. If electricity prices and carbon intensity are low, sacrificing electricity production to supply heat for the capture process is a lower cost heat supply strategy than investing in additional boiler capacity and combusting biomass. However, if electricity prices are high, the opposite is true. When considering current electricity prices and emissions intensities, applying the cost-optimal heat supply scenario to each mill reduces the estimated avoidance cost for sector-wide CCS implementation by 3-4 % compared to applying the same heat supply strategy to all of the mills. When the cost estimation is performed to reflect an electricity system that has transitioned towards generally lower costs and emissions intensity, the Minimized fuel use scenario results in consistently lower avoidance costs, with the exception of one mill. This indicates that combusting biomass to supply heat for the capture process can be more cost-effective in the near term, while the cost optimal long-term strategy could be to bypass turbines in order to generate the required steam.

Additionally, the distance between the mill and a suitable harbour for shipping the CO₂ to a permanent sequestration site is shown to have a large effect on the total CDR cost, especially if (shared or stand-alone) onshore pipelines are not available as a transport option (which can be expected to be the case in the near term). Thus, the results presented in this report highlight the importance of regional factors in determining the cost of bio-CCS.

To facilitate CO₂ capture implementation in pulp and paper mills, investigation of practical considerations at individual mills are necessary. Impurities in the flue gas stream from black liquor combustion could present technical difficulties and additional costs for flue gas cleaning that are not accounted for in the present work, but nonetheless of high importance for the feasibility of large-scale CCS implementation in the pulp and paper industry.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Document Purpose.....	2
1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations.....	2
1.3 Relation to other deliverables	2
2 OVERVIEW OF THE EUROPEAN PULP AND PAPER INDUSTRY	3
3 BIOGENIC EMISSIONS FROM EUROPEAN PULP AND PAPER MILLS	4
3.1 Flue gas impurities associated with black liquor combustion	6
4 TECHNO-ECONOMIC EVALUATION	8
4.1 Estimation of CO ₂ removal, CO ₂ emissions avoidance and Costs.....	8
4.2 Assumptions regarding emissions sources and CO ₂ concentrations	8
4.3 Cost data and assumptions for steam and electricity supply	9
5 MARGINAL COST OF CO ₂ EMISSIONS AVOIDANCE	13
5.1 First-of-a-kind (FOAK)	13
5.2 N th -of-a-kind (NOAK).....	16
5.3 Impact of Geographical Location	18
6 CONCLUSIONS	21
7 REFERENCES	22

1 INTRODUCTION

To comply with the targets outlined in the Paris Agreement of limiting global warming to 2°C and pursuing efforts to keep warming below 1.5°C, deep emissions reductions, along with carbon dioxide removal (CDR), are required. All pathways investigated by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) that limit warming to below 1.5°C rely on CDR at the gigatonne scale by 2050 [1]. The pulp and paper industry, and specifically kraft pulp mills, has a large potential for CDR via bio-CCS (e.g., approximately 62 MtCO₂/a of biogenic emissions that could be captured [2]) due to the prevalence of large point sources of biogenic CO₂ with relatively high CO₂ concentration. Previous work that conducted sector-wide techno-economic assessment in the Swedish context (a country with a large and active forest industry) evaluated the CO₂ capture costs from large industrial facilities (> 500 ktCO₂/a) including the pulp and paper industry [3], [4]. Such studies typically find that large pulp and paper mills present cost-effective opportunities for CO₂ capture implementation. However, to facilitate implementation, further understanding of factors affecting the potential and costs need to be investigated and discussed. Thus, the overall aim of this work is to assess the potential and cost for CDR from the pulp and paper industry at the European level, considering regional and geographical conditions (e.g., different energy prices and CO₂ transportation opportunities) and the impact of different heat integration scenarios.

Previous work in the ACCSESS project reported in deliverable D5.3 [5] performed case studies investigating CO₂ capture costs for two case study mills, one recycled paper mill located in Langerbrugge, Belgium, and one kraft pulp mill in Skutskär, Sweden, based on different heat integration scenarios presented in deliverable D5.2 [6]. Evaluations were conducted considering two different post-combustion CO₂ capture technologies, an amine-based (AMP/PZ) and an enzymatic carbonate-based capture technology. The cost estimation showed that the cost-optimal technology is highly context dependent, especially with respect to energy prices (electricity and fuel), availability of residual heat from the mill that can be used to drive the capture plant, and the chosen strategy for heat integration. Additionally, future investments in technologies to valorize the carbon content of the feedstock, such as lignin extraction, will further impact the cost-optimal capture solution.

This report presents results on the potential and costs for CDR via bio-CCS from the European pulp and paper industry, considering sites with biogenic emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. By setting the cut-off criteria at 250 kt/a of biogenic CO₂, 58 of the 856 European pulp and paper mills are included in the analysis. While this is a small share of the total number of mills, the selection covers the large biogenic emitters in the sector, including primarily kraft pulp producers. Most of the excluded mills produce paper and board with no integrated pulp production, and some are mechanical pulp/paper or recycled pulp producers. The majority of the excluded mills have minor or no biogenic CO₂ emissions. For the selected mills, the report presents geographically resolved potential for bio-CCS, along with costs for CO₂ capture, conditioning and transportation considering the AMP/PZ post-combustion capture technology. Focusing on AMP/PZ for CO₂ capture in this work is motivated by the results in D5.3 which investigated post-combustion capture technologies using an amine-based solvent (AMP/PZ) and a carbonate-based solvent (CO₂ Solutions). The work reported in D5.3 showed that neither of the technologies investigated is clearly better than the other, and that the choice of cost-optimal capture technology is dependent on site-specific factors and the context in which the technology is installed (e.g., energy prices). Thus, choosing to investigate a benchmark solvent such as AMP/PZ, is reasonable when scaling up to the European level, since many assumptions need to be made and site-specific conditions

for each individual mill are unknown. In the analysis performed in this work, different heat integration scenarios based on learnings from previous work performed in D5.3 are investigated.

1.1 Document Purpose

This report presents results from Work Package 5 (WP5), Task 5.4 of the ACCESS project. The purpose of the report is to give an assessment of the potential quantities and associated costs for CDR from the European pulp and paper industry, considering mills with annual biogenic CO₂ emissions above 250 kt/a.

1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations

AMP/PZ	AMP (2-amino-2-methyl-propanol) -PZ (piperazine)
BAT	Best available techniques
bio-CCS	Biogenic carbon capture and storage
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CDR	Carbon dioxide removal
CEPI	Confederation of European Paper Industries
E-PRTR	European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCOA	Levelized cost of avoidance
LCOR	Levelized cost of removal

1.3 Relation to other deliverables

The work in this deliverable builds upon previous work performed in WP5 reported in deliverables D5.2 and D5.3. The work in this deliverable extends the cost analysis to cover the European pulp and paper sector and utilizes the results and learnings from the heat integration scenarios in D5.2 and D5.3.

2 OVERVIEW OF THE EUROPEAN PULP AND PAPER INDUSTRY

In 2023, there were over 850 pulp and paper mills in operation in Europe, the vast majority (83 %) of which were paper mills [7]. The sector emitted around 27 Mt/a of fossil CO₂ in 2022, and has been estimated to have biogenic emissions of around 62 Mt/a [2]. The most used fuels in the sector were biomass and natural gas, making up approximately 55% and 28% of the sector's total primary energy consumption, while net imported electricity accounted for around 11% [7].

The pulp and paper industry consists of mills producing pulp, paper or a combination of the two. Pulp mills that also produce paper are typically referred to as integrated mills. The raw materials used to produce pulp are either pulpwood or recycled paper. Two main categories of pathways are used for producing pulp, chemical or mechanical pulping. Mechanical pulping is typically energy-intensive, often using electricity as the main energy source to drive the process. Thus, the direct CO₂ emissions from mechanical pulping are typically lower than for chemical pulping. Chemical pulping is dominated by the kraft pulping process. In kraft pulp mills, cooking chemicals are recovered through combustion of black liquor in recovery boilers, leading to substantial emissions of biogenic CO₂. Lime kilns are also used in the chemical recovery process, which leads to additional CO₂ emissions at relatively high concentrations, although lower volumes than from recovery boilers. Thus, kraft pulp mills, and specifically recovery boilers, are the major source of biogenic CO₂ from pulp production. For a typical kraft pulp mill, the recovery boiler accounts for roughly 75% of site emissions, while the lime kiln and bark boiler make up around 10-15 % respectively [4]. The bark boiler typically operates intermittently throughout the year, based on the mill's internal steam demand.

It should be noted here that there are other chemical processes for pulp production than the kraft process, most notably different types of sulfite cooking. However, these production methods are significantly less common than kraft pulp production, hence the focus on describing the kraft pulping process in more detail.

3 BIOGENIC EMISSIONS FROM EUROPEAN PULP AND PAPER MILLS

This section outlines the estimation performed to assess the potential for CDR from European pulp and paper plants. In this work, the focus has been to study mills with biogenic emissions over 250 ktCO₂/a, since smaller emissions sources are likely to be significantly more expensive and thus less relevant for cost-effective CDR implementation.

Since the potential for CDR is given by the biogenic CO₂ emissions, the biogenic CO₂ emissions from the pulp and paper sector need to be estimated. Figure 3.1 illustrates the approach taken to estimate the biogenic CO₂ emissions from pulp and paper mills in this work. The estimation performed is based on data for year 2022 extracted from the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR), data from individual company websites and environmental reports, and assumptions based on the type of production at a given site. If biogenic emissions are reported to the E-PRTR, this data was used. If not, environmental reports from the individual company were consulted as an additional source of data related to biogenic emissions. If biogenic emissions were missing in both the E-PRTR and environmental reports (or if the environmental reports could not be found), an estimation of the biogenic emissions was made based on the annual production rate and type of production at the mill.

There is no obligation to report biogenic CO₂ emissions, or to differentiate between fossil and biogenic emissions in reporting to the E-PRTR. However, mills in Sweden and Finland, the two largest pulp producing countries in Europe, report both biogenic and fossil CO₂ emissions to the E-PRTR. The type of production (sometimes including production capacities) was retrieved from company websites.

Figure 3.1. Decision tree for the estimation of biogenic CO₂ emissions performed in this work.

Figure 3.2 shows the pulp and paper mills included in this work based on the selection criteria and methodology described previously in this Section and Figure 3.1. In total, there are 58 mills emitting between 250 and 3300 ktCO₂/a (see Table A1 in the Appendix for more information on the individual mills). In total, the mills included in the analysis emit around 55 MtCO₂/a. Most of the included sites, 49 out of the total 58, are kraft pulp mills, with large biogenic emissions emanating primarily from the recovery boiler. The total emissions from recovery boilers are estimated at close to 40 MtCO₂/a. The sites are largely located along the coastline, or along waterways that are connected to the coast. This is especially true for the kraft pulp mills producing market pulp, since this is a commodity that is often transported long distances to reach a paper mill. In central Europe and the UK, the prevalence of recycled paper mills, mechanical pulp mills, and paper mills is higher. These sites typically emit lower amounts of biogenic CO₂ than kraft pulp mills. Among the mills covered in the analysis, there are also a few mills producing sulfite pulp and chemi-thermo-mechanical pulp (CTMP). However, the production volumes for these pulp types are vastly outnumbered by the production of kraft, mechanical and recycled pulp. The mills that lack access to the coast, either directly or via a river, typically have railway connections, to allow for the in-and outflow of feedstock and products.

Figure 3.2. Mapping of biogenic emissions from the pulp and paper mills considered in this work.

Figure 3.3 shows a) the number of mills and b) the annual biogenic CO₂ emissions from the mills considered for each country in Europe. As can be seen in Figure 3.3, the pulp and paper industry, and thus the emissions, are primarily located in Sweden and Finland. In addition to the high biogenic emissions in Sweden and Finland that could be captured for the purposes of CDR, these countries also have relatively low grid emissions intensity and relatively good conditions for CO₂ transport to permanent storage sites in the North Sea region via the Baltic Sea. Additionally, since Sweden and Finland have active forest industries, waste streams such as branches and tops that currently have an unutilized potential, could be used to generate heat for the capture process.

Figure 3.3. The number of mills (panel a) and annual biogenic emissions (panel b) for all European countries with mills emitting more than 250 ktCO₂/a.

3.1 Flue gas impurities associated with black liquor combustion

Most of the mills considered in this analysis are kraft pulp mills for which the primary emissions source is the recovery boiler. Recovery boilers combust black liquor that contain (in addition to C, H, O and N) large amounts of inorganics, mainly sodium (Na, typically 15-20 wt% (dry basis)), as well as significant quantities of potassium (K), sulfur (S) and chlorine (Cl) [8].

Consequently, black liquor combustion results in an array of polluting emissions (that may react with amines), more specifically:

- SO₂ and other S-containing compounds
- NO_x
- Dust/particulates, both fine/fume and carry-over/coarse particles, mainly made of Na₂SO₄ and some alkali chlorides
- CO
- HCl (usually low, likewise for HF)
- Trace metals (usually very low for most metals)
- (TOC, PAH, dioxins/furans have been investigated in some studies)

Both primary measures and requisite flue gas cleaning measures, e.g. electrostatic precipitator (ESP) for particles, are implemented to ensure that emissions remain below the limits set by regulatory bodies (see BAT PP reference document [9] for more details).

Emissions may vary with the properties of the black liquor, operating conditions and the gas cleaning processes selected. Typical values are given in the BAT PP reference document [9] for

key compounds: 1 – 100 mg/Nm³ for SO₂ (annual average, standardized reference 6% O₂); 0-50 mg/Nm³ for total reduced sulfur TRS (same reference); 120-250 mg/Nm³ for NO_x (same reference, using only primary measures, SCR/SNCR are not used in the sector) and 5-190 mg/Nm³ for particulates after electrostatic precipitator (same reference). CO concentrations typically vary between 10 mg/Nm³ and 100 mg/Nm³ as a yearly average value for most mills.

It should also be noted that many mills operate the recovery boiler with between 3 % and 6 % oxygen content (with 19% being a typical value for CO₂, dry basis).

An important feature of recovery boilers is that emissions may exhibit significant variations/fluctuations (both between plants and at a given plant) and that peaks (at least for some species) are not uncommon.

Given the large spectrum of possible components in recovery flue gas streams, and given the relatively limited experience of capturing CO₂ from this type of source, there are good reasons to expect that additional/optimized gas cleaning may be necessary to ensure satisfactory operation for the carbon capture unit.

4 TECHNO-ECONOMIC EVALUATION

4.1 Estimation of CO₂ removal, CO₂ emissions avoidance and Costs

The cost estimations performed in this work use the iCCS toolset [10] to calculate the costs for CO₂ capture and conditioning based on the flue gas flow rate and CO₂ concentration, as well as for the cost of CO₂ storage offshore. For CO₂ transportation and storage, cost estimations are based on work by Oeuvray et al. [11] to ensure consistency within the ACCSESS project. The cost estimation is performed both on a first-of-a-kind (FOAK) and nth-of-a-kind (NOAK) basis, representing different conditions in terms of the assumed technological maturity. The FOAK cost estimates aim to better represent conditions faced by industrial actors implementing CO₂ capture technology in the near term. For capture and conditioning, this is done primarily by applying higher contingency factors, a higher discount rate, and lower economic lifetime of the technology in the FOAK case than in the NOAK case. For the economic assumptions related to FOAK and NOAK installations, we have followed the assumptions from Becattini et al., [12]. For transportation and storage, ship transportation at 7 barg and the use of onshore pipelines is assumed to be available for the NOAK case. For the FOAK case, ship transportation is assumed to take place at 15 barg and onshore transportation is limited to the use of trucks, since these technologies are likely to be available in the near term.

To compare the costs generated in different scenarios, the Levelized Cost Of Avoidance (LCOA) and Levelized Cost Of Removal (LCOR) are calculated according to Equation 1 and Equation 2 respectively. In Eqs. (1) and (2), C_{tot}^{CCS} denotes the total annual cost (including both CAPEX and OPEX) for the CCS chain, including capture, conditioning, transportation and permanent storage. The avoided ($m_{CO_2,avoided}$) and removed ($m_{CO_2,removed}$) CO₂ emissions are calculated according to Eqs. (3) and (4). Avoided CO₂ emissions are based on the total CO₂ emissions captured at the mill (including both biogenic and fossil CO₂), the CO₂ removal only accounts for the biogenic CO₂, which contributes to CDR. Both emissions avoidance and removal account for the (fossil) CO₂ emissions resulting from electricity or fuel use in the capture, conditioning, transportation and permanent storage of CO₂, $m_{CO_2,emitted,CCS}$.

$$LCOA = \frac{C_{tot}^{CCS}}{m_{CO_2,avoided}} \quad [€/tCO_2] \quad (1)$$

$$LCOR = \frac{C_{tot}^{CCS}}{m_{CO_2,removed}} \quad [€/tCO_2] \quad (2)$$

$$m_{CO_2,avoided} = m_{CO_2,total,captured} - m_{CO_2,emitted,fossil,CCS} \quad [tCO_2/a] \quad (3)$$

$$m_{CO_2,removed} = m_{CO_2,biogenic,captured} - m_{CO_2,emitted,fossil,CCS} \quad [tCO_2/a] \quad (4)$$

It is worth noting that the cost of pre-treatment of the flue gas is not included here. Costs of SO_x and NO_x have been shown to be typically low [13]. The cost of removing heavy metals (such as nickel, vanadium, and lead) was estimated to lie between 0.5 and 2 €/tCO₂ based on Gumerman et al. [14] and Utku et al. [15].

4.2 Assumptions regarding emissions sources and CO₂ concentrations

Table 4.1 presents the assumptions regarding the CO₂ sources at different types of mill and the CO₂ concentration in the combined flue gas, used for calculating the CO₂ capture cost. For kraft

mills, the assumptions are based on previous work that investigated CO₂ capture in (among other industries) the pulp and paper industry [4], [16]. At kraft mills, most of the site emissions come from the recovery boiler. However, a relatively large share of the flue gases also originates from the lime kiln, which has a higher CO₂ concentration due to process emissions from the calcination process. Consequently, the CO₂ concentration of the combined flue gases in a kraft pulp mill is estimated to be slightly higher than for sites with emissions from combustion only. Typically, kraft mills operate with close to 100% biogenic CO₂ emissions, since the use of “top-up” fossil fuels has been largely phased out today. For other mills, emissions are assumed to originate from a boiler fired with biomass fuel for the few cases where no other information was found in environmental reports or emissions accounting. For the purposes of the techno-economic assessment performed in this work, a capture rate of 90% was assumed.

Table 4.1. Assumptions applied in this work regarding flue gas sources and combined CO₂ concentration for different mill types.

Mill type	Flue gas sources	Combined CO ₂ concentration [%]
Kraft mill (pulp or pulp and paper)	Recovery boiler	15
	Lime kiln	
	Bark boiler	
Mechanical pulp / pulp and paper mill	Boiler	13
Recycled fiber	Boiler	13
Paper mill	Boiler	13
Other chemical mills	Combined stack	13

4.3 Cost data and assumptions for steam and electricity supply

4.3.1 Heat integration scenarios

Industrial steam systems typically consist of several steam headers with different pressure levels that can supply steam for use in internal processes. One or more boilers generate high pressure (HP) steam which can be expanded in a turbine with extraction points that enable steam to be fed to medium pressure (MP) or low pressure (LP) steam headers. In addition, the option to bypass the turbine(s) and throttle the steam through a valve to lower pressure levels is typically present (which is an isenthalpic process). Note that there may be additional steam headers, and that the configuration of the steam system can vary significantly between sites. For absorption-based CCS applications such as the one explored in this work, LP steam (around 3-4 bar) condenses at a suitable temperature for satisfying the heat demand of the capture process.

Most of the mills identified as large emitters of biogenic CO₂ are kraft pulp and paper mills. In a kraft mill, HP steam is mainly produced in the recovery boiler. In addition to producing steam, the recovery boiler is also a key process in the recovery of cooking chemicals from the black liquor, a by-product from the pulping process. The resulting steam production is consequently determined by the requirement to process black liquor for chemicals recovery and therefore not adjusted in response to steam demand variations.

For the cost estimations performed in this work, the heat integration scenarios presented in Table 4.2 were applied. For the **Reference scenario**, no heat integration is considered between the industrial site and the capture process. A stand-alone biomass boiler is assumed to be installed to

supply the required heat to the reboiler as LP steam. This biomass boiler and LP steam generated is not connected to the existing steam network. This scenario is calculated to establish a baseline for calculating the additional cost and biomass use for large-scale implementation of bio-CCS in the pulp and paper sector if no heat integration is considered. New biomass boilers are assumed to be heat-only, i.e. it is assumed that the additional investment cost for high-pressure steam production and turbines would not be motivated. Additionally, it is assumed that the CO₂ emitted from the additional combustion of biomass is not captured.

The **minimized fuel use scenario** draws upon the learnings from work done in the ACCESS project and detailed in deliverable D5.3. In the minimized fuel use scenario, it is assumed that the CO₂ capture process is integrated with the host site, and that the heat required for the reboiler in the capture plants is supplied by LP steam. A simplified flowsheet of the LP steam generation in the minimized fuel use scenario is shown in blue in Figure 4.1. In the Minimized fuel use scenario it is assumed that there is no excess of LP steam available in the mill and that the mill process is highly energy efficient, meaning that there is no scope for direct recovery of residual heat from the process. Consequently, all LP steam for the capture process must be generated. In this scenario, it is assumed that the required LP steam is generated by bypassing the steam turbine (red in Figure 4.1), throttling the steam from HP to LP pressure levels, and subsequent de-superheating (shown in blue in Figure 4.1). This means that the electricity that would have been generated between the live steam and LP pressure levels is sacrificed in favor of satisfying the reboiler heat demand. Since throttling is an isenthalpic process, the additional energy content that is generated in the form of LP steam by bypassing the turbine is equivalent to the electricity production that is sacrificed by bypassing the turbine (assuming that mechanical losses in turbines and generators are negligible).

Table 4.2. Heat integration scenarios considered in this work.

Scenario	Description
Reference	No heat integration is considered between the mill and the capture plant. The additional heat demand imposed by CO ₂ capture is covered by combustion of residual biomass in a new, stand-alone biomass heat-only boiler.
Minimized fuel use	The CO ₂ capture process is integrated with the host plant in a way that minimizes the additional fuel use required to drive the CO ₂ capture. HP steam is throttled and fed to the LP header, thereby reducing the electricity output, since steam turbines are bypassed.

Figure 4.1. Simplified flowsheet illustrating the steam-flow in the Minimized fuel use scenario. The blue part illustrates LP steam generation by extracting live steam, bypassing steam turbines (red), throttling the steam and subsequent de-superheating.

An alternative integrated scenario could have been to increase the production of HP steam in a biomass boiler and thereby maintain or even increase electricity production at the expense of increased fuel costs and potentially investments in a new boiler and back-pressure turbine. To avoid speculation about available capacity in existing boilers, which is expected to differ significantly between mills, this scenario was excluded from the present study. The results from Task 5.3 showed that costs could be similar for scenarios that minimize fuel use or maintain or maximize back-pressure power production, but this is very sensitive to assumptions about electricity prices. Additionally, the advantage of the chosen approach for the integrated scenario is that no additional fuel must be combusted to maintain operation of the mill's production processes and the CO₂ capture process.

The two scenarios combined span a range of possible outcomes regarding biomass demand and electricity generation. The reference scenario presents a high level of additional biomass demand for the capture plant, while the minimized fuel use scenario results in a low level of additional biomass demand. On the other hand, the reference scenario results in no changes in electricity generation, while the minimized fuel use scenario leads to significant reductions in electricity generation.

4.3.2 Energy price and emissions data

Table 4.3 presents the main country-specific data assumptions applied in this work, where the electricity prices and electricity emissions intensity are differentiated between the FOAK and NOAK cases. Where possible, the assumptions in this work are aligned with the assumptions applied by Becattini et al. [12]. However, since this analysis covers mills located in countries that are not included within their analysis, complementary data sources are used when needed. Labor costs are calculated based on hourly labor cost and work time data from Eurostat [17], [18], with a similar approach to that adopted by Becattini et al [12]. and to cover all countries included in the analysis. For the electricity price and emissions intensity applied in the FOAK cost estimates, we complement the available data, with data from Eurostat [19] and Statista [20]. For electricity prices and emissions intensity used in the NOAK estimates, we use data based on the Energy systems model EMPIRE, developed by NTNU [21], with the prices and emissions intensity applied in this work representing results from year 2030-2035. Overall, the electricity prices and emissions intensities applied in the NOAK cost estimates are lower than in the FOAK estimates, since they reflect prices in a system that has higher levels of lower cost and lower emitting generation technologies.

The capital cost for a biomass heat-only boiler, used to calculate the steam supply cost in the Reference scenario, is based on the heat demand ($\dot{Q}_{MW_{th}}$ in MW) according to Eq. (5), taken from D5.3 [5] representing the cost for a fluidized bed boiler.

$$C = 471 \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_{MW_{th}}}{1521} \right)^{0.67} \text{ [M\$]} \quad (5)$$

Table 4.3. Country specific cost data applied in the cost estimation performed in this work.

Country	Used in FOAK estimates		Used in NOAK estimates		Labor costs [k€/year]
	Electricity price [€/MWh]	Electricity emissions intensity [kgCO ₂ /MWh]	Electricity price [€/MWh]	Electricity emissions intensity [kgCO ₂ /MWh]	
Austria	82.8	110.8	30.7	10.8	86.4
Belgium	64.1	138.1	37.1	114.6	94.8
Bulgaria	64.7	335.3	32.8	216.6	17.5
Finland	50.8	79.2	20.8	49.3	80.2
France	59.2	56.0	28.9	23.2	87.6
Germany	106.5	381.2	35.2	272.8	89.5
Portugal	73.4	165.6	27.4	21.9	29.3
Spain	63.1	174.1	29.9	53.5	52.0
Sweden	40.5	40.7	21.7	69.1	85.8
UK	136.3	128.7	31.1	99.7	67.4

The price for biomass fuel (wood chips) is assumed to be 35 €/MWh, which is between the recent spot prices reported on the Baltic spot market for wood fuels (Baltpool) [22], and the price levels for Northwestern Europe [23]. For fossil CO₂ emissions related to biomass use, the assumptions from the ACCESS framework were applied. The emissions intensity from using a biomass boiler, i.e., fossil emissions emanating from the boiler construction, was assumed to be the same for Sweden and Finland, i.e. 5.8 kgCO₂/GJ, whereas biomass in the rest of Europe was assumed to have the same emissions intensity as in Germany, 8.3 kgCO₂/GJ. Note that these numbers do not include direct biogenic emissions from biomass combustion, since these are considered carbon neutral in the calculation of LCOA and LCOR.

5 MARGINAL COST OF CO₂ EMISSIONS AVOIDANCE

5.1 First-of-a-kind (FOAK)

Figure 5.1 presents the LCOA (bars) and LCOR (diamonds) for the Reference scenario, applying the FOAK assumptions and input parameters. The estimated levelized avoidance costs presented in Figure 5.1 range between 152-330 €/tCO₂ avoided. For most mills, LCOA and LCOR are equivalent, or very similar. This is because most of the studied mills have very low fossil CO₂ emissions, making the CO₂ avoidance and removal equal (see Equations 3-4). There are a few exceptions where LCOR is significantly higher than LCOA, which represents mills with a relatively high share of fossil emissions (15-33%) located in Belgium, Germany and Spain.

In Figure 5.1, the major contribution to LCOA is the cost for the CO₂ capture process. Looking solely at the cost contribution of the capture process, the effect of economies of scale can be observed, where mills with large emissions have a lower capture cost than mills with lower emissions. However, in determining the total avoidance cost, transportation also makes a significant contribution, showing that not only the scale of the mill, but also its location, are important in determining the overall avoidance cost. Furthermore, the distribution between onshore and offshore transport varies widely between the different mills. The onshore transportation costs are highly sensitive to the distance between the mills and the departing harbor, due to the use of trucks for onshore transportation in the FOAK case.

In the reference scenario, a stand-alone heat-only biomass boiler is assumed to supply the heat required for the capture process. In total, approximately 40 TWh/a of additional biomass are estimated to be required to supply the heat required for CO₂ capture at all investigated mills. This would entail a significant increase from the roughly 245 TWh of biomass consumed in the EU's industrial sector in 2021 [24]. Assuming an emissions factor for biomass combustion of 346 kgCO₂/MWh (same assumption as used by Jönsson & Berntsson [25]), combustion of 40 TWh/a of biomass would give additional biogenic emissions of just below 14 MtCO₂/a, a significant share of the CO₂ removal of 44 Mt/a in this scenario.

Figure 5.1. Marginal avoidance cost curve for the Reference scenario applying the FOAK cost estimation assumptions for European pulp and paper mills with emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. The diamond markers indicate the levelized removal cost of CO₂ for each mill.

Figure 5.2 presents LCOA (bars) and LCOR (diamonds) for the Minimized fuel use scenario, which assumes that the heat demand for the capture process is met by LP steam generated by bypassing steam turbines, applying the FOAK cost assumptions. The estimated LCOA varies widely between the mills, spanning a range of 140-534 €/tCO₂ avoided. The wide range of the estimated costs presented in Figure 5.2 are explained by the sensitivity of the capture cost in the Minimized fuel use scenario to the electricity price, since the heat demand for the capture process is satisfied by sacrificing electricity production.

The five mills presenting the lowest estimated LCOA in the Reference scenario (Figure 5.1), are mills located in Sweden (four mills) and Finland (one mill). These five mills are sorted at place 1, 2, 3, 5 and 13 respectively in the Minimized fuel use scenario (Figure 5.2). The three mills sorted at places 1-3 according to ascending LCOA in both scenarios are located in southern Sweden along the coastline. For these three mills, it can thus be concluded that with the given assumptions, the heat supply strategy does not impact the relative cost-competitiveness of CCS implementation. Furthermore, bypassing the turbines to supply heat for capture in these mills is seen to slightly decrease the estimated LCOA compared to a heat supply strategy with additional LP steam production in a biomass boiler. This is due to the relatively low electricity price and electricity emissions intensity in Sweden, making the use of a biomass boiler slightly less cost-effective than the sacrificing electricity production to supply heat to the capture process. However, the opposite applies for mills located in countries where the electricity price and electricity emissions intensity is higher, for instance Germany, Bulgaria and to a lesser extent Portugal and Spain.

Further comparing Figures 5.1 and 5.2, the total CO₂ avoidance is just above 45 Mt/a in the reference scenario, while being just below 43 Mt/a in the minimized fuel use scenario. The lower CO₂ avoidance in the minimized fuel use scenario is due to the sacrificed electricity production leading to higher Scope 2 emissions. This effect is especially pronounced in countries with high electricity grid emissions intensity. On the other hand, the reference scenario, as mentioned above, will require additional use of biomass associated with approximately 14 Mt/a of additional (non-captured) biogenic CO₂ emissions, which are not included in the CO₂ avoidance estimation. Depending on how the biomass is sourced, this biomass usage could potentially make less biomass available for substitution of fossil fuels in other applications. Since biomass is a limited resource, utilizing it for the purpose of producing steam might not be the best use case, especially if the demand for green chemicals increases in the future, for example.

Furthermore, the range of LCOR (diamonds) shown in Figures 5.1 and 5.2 is lower than the estimated FOAK cost range of \$400-\$700 for direct air capture (DAC) reported by the IEAGHG [26], indicating that bio-CCS from the pulp and paper industry could present cost-effective opportunities for CDR.

Figure 5.2. Marginal avoidance cost curve for the Minimized fuel use scenario applying the FOAK cost estimation for European pulp and paper mills with emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. The diamond markers indicate the cost of CO₂ removal for each mill.

Figure 5.3 shows the LCOA for the mills covered in this study, applying the FOAK cost assumptions, displaying the cost for the lowest-cost heat supply strategy at each individual mill. For most of the mills with low avoidance costs, the strategy of minimizing fuel (i.e., sacrificing electricity production in favor of generating steam for the capture process), is the least-cost solution. This is due to these mills being located in regions with low electricity prices, e.g., Sweden.

For any individual mill, applying the cost-optimal heat supply strategy can reduce the avoidance cost by up to 30% compared to the non-optimal case. For the sector as a whole, applying the cost-optimal heat supply scenario to each mill reduces the estimated avoidance cost for sector-wide CCS implementation by 3-4 % compared to applying the same heat supply strategy to all of the mills.

Figure 5.3. Marginal avoidance cost curve showing the cost-optimal heat supply scenario for European pulp and paper mills with emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a, applying the FOAK cost estimation assumptions.

5.2 Nth-of-a-kind (NOAK)

Figure 5.4 presents the LCOA (bars) and LCOR (diamonds) for the mills considered in this work in the Reference scenario for the NOAK cost assumptions. In Figure 5.4 the estimated avoidance costs span between 105-165 €/tCO₂ avoided. Like the results presented in Figure 5.1, the capture cost contributes most significantly to the total avoidance cost. In contrast to the FOAK cost estimates, the onshore, and to a lesser extent offshore, transportation makes up a smaller part of the total cost when the NOAK assumptions are applied. This is due to the assumed availability of pipelines for onshore transportation, and the use of 7 barg transportation for shipping.

Furthermore, the estimated LCOA in Figure 5.4 spans a narrower range than the FOAK counterpart in Figure 5.1. This is again primarily an effect of the lower onshore transportation cost which reduces the spread of estimated LCOA between the different mills.

Figure 5.4. Marginal avoidance cost curve for the Reference scenario applying the NOAK cost estimation assumptions for European pulp and paper mills with emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. The diamond markers indicate the cost of CO₂ removal for each mill.

Figure 5.5 presents the levelized cost of CO₂ avoidance for the minimized fuel use scenario. The estimated avoidance costs in the minimized fuel use scenario range between 85-175 €/tCO₂ avoided. Comparing the estimated LCOA in Figure 5.4 and 5.5, the Minimized fuel use scenario results in consistently lower avoidance costs, with the exception of one mill. This is due to the sensitivity of the costs to electricity prices, which are consistently lower for the NOAK cost assumptions. The applied electricity prices are based on results from European-wide energy systems modelling, using the average modelled prices for 2030-2035. Thus, in a future scenario where electricity prices and emissions intensity are low, it is more cost-effective to sacrifice electricity generation to supply the heat demand imposed by the capture process. However, combusting additional biomass to supply heat for the capture process can be more cost-effective in the near term, if electricity prices are high.

The results highlight that access to low-cost electricity and short transportation distances are important factors in determining cost-optimal locations for bio-CCS from pulp and paper mills. Furthermore, the most cost-effective strategy for supplying heat to the capture process will be dependent upon the regional energy price conditions, and the development of the future energy systems, specifically, the relative cost trajectories of electricity compared to biomass.

Figure 5.5. Marginal avoidance cost curve for the Minimized fuel use scenario applying the NOAK cost estimation assumptions for European pulp and paper mills with emissions above 250 ktCO₂/a. The diamond markers indicate the cost of CO₂ removal for each mill.

5.3 Impact of Geographical Location

Figure 5.6 presents the national average LCOA for the mills included in the study applying the FOAK cost assumptions in a) the Reference scenario and b) the Minimized fuel use scenario. The figure shows that Sweden is the only country for which LCOA is lower for the minimized fuel use scenario compared to the Reference scenario. This implies that the cost-optimal heat supply strategy, with assumptions for electricity prices representative of FOAK conditions, is to combust additional biomass to supply heat for the capture process, in all countries except Sweden. However, in Sweden, sacrificing electricity production in favor of supplying heat for the CO₂ capture process, is more favorable due to the lower electricity price and emissions intensity. It should be noted here that although Sweden is only one out of the ten countries included in this work, 24 out of 58 mills are located in Sweden.

In Figure 5.6, the country with the most significant difference in average LCOA between the two scenarios is Germany, with an average LCOA of 231 €/tCO₂ and 415 €/tCO₂ in the Reference scenario and Minimized fuel use scenario respectively. This large difference is explained by the relative cost of electricity in Germany compared to biomass when the FOAK cost assumptions are applied. In the FOAK assumptions for electricity price and emissions intensity, Germany is the country with the highest electricity emissions intensity, and the second highest electricity price (see Table 4.3). Put together, these factors result in the LCOA being significantly higher when electricity production is sacrificed to supply heat to the capture process, compared to when biomass is combusted to supply the required heat.

Figure 5.6. National average LCOA applying the FOAK cost assumptions in a) the Reference scenario, and b) the Minimized fuel use scenario.

Figure 5.7 shows the share of emissions avoidance that can be achieved at different avoidance cost levels (spanning from < 200 to < 350 €/tCO₂ avoided) when the FOAK cost assumptions, and the Reference heat integration scenario are applied. At the lowest displayed cost range < 200 €/t, it can be observed that implementation covering around 28% of the emissions could be implemented in Finland and Portugal, around 60-75% in Sweden and the UK and 100% in Bulgaria (although this represents only 1 mill). As the cost cut-off is increased toward 250 and 300 €/tCO₂ avoided, large-scale implementation could potentially be achieved in most of the countries investigated. This implies that, given practical feasibility of implementation and with the assumptions applied here, an income stream through carbon prices of around 250-300 €/tCO₂, could give economic incentives for large scale CO₂ capture deployment among the mills covered in this analysis. Note that the results in Figure 5.7 consider the FOAK cost assumptions and the use of a biomass boiler to supply heat for CO₂ capture.

Figure 5.7. Share of emissions avoidance that can be achieved at different cost cut-offs for Reference scenario applying the FOAK cost assumptions.

Figure 5.8 presents the national average LCOA for the mills included in the study applying the NOAK cost assumptions in a) the Reference scenario and b) the Minimized fuel use scenario. In contrast to the results presented in Figure 5.6, the Minimized fuel use scenario yields the lowest LCOA for all countries except for Germany with the NOAK cost assumptions. Thus, if the future electricity system evolves towards lower prices and lower emissions intensity, sacrificing electricity production to drive the capture process becomes the cost-optimal solution to supply steam to drive the capture process in most regions. With the NOAK cost assumptions, the difference in national average avoidance cost is 20 €/tCO₂ or more in five out of the ten countries comparing the Minimized fuel use scenario compared to the Reference scenario.

Figure 5.8. National average LCOA applying the NOAK cost assumptions in a) the Reference scenario, and b) the Minimized fuel use scenario.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this report was performed within WP5 of the ACCESS project. The purpose of the work was to present an estimation of the potential and costs for CDR from the European pulp and paper industry, focusing on sites with biogenic emissions over 250 ktCO₂/a. Furthermore, the work considered two different strategies for producing the steam required to provide heat to drive the capture process. One strategy involves combusting biomass in a stand-alone biomass boiler, and the other strategy is to bypass the mill's steam turbines, thereby sacrificing electricity production to supply the heat demand imposed by the capture process. It should be noted that the estimates for CDR potential and cost presented in this report are subject to practical considerations, such as the need for additional flue gas cleaning at any individual mill. Impurities in the flue gas stream from black liquor combustion could present technical difficulties and additional costs that are not accounted for in the present work, but nonetheless of high importance for the practical feasibility of large-scale CCS implementation in the pulp and paper industry.

The estimation of biogenic emissions from the pulp and paper sector carried out in this work showed that the biogenic emissions, and thus the potential for CDR, are mainly concentrated in Sweden and Finland, where there is an active forestry industry and a large prevalence of kraft pulp mills. In total, the biogenic emissions (which constitute the theoretical potential for CDR) from the mills included in the analysis are around 55 MtCO₂/a. Assuming a 90% capture rate, it was concluded that it should be possible to capture up to 50 MtCO₂/a. Kraft pulp mills make up a majority of the biogenic emissions, being 49 out of the 58 mills covered in this analysis, and contributing around 48 out of the 55 MtCO₂/a.

The work also included a techno-economic assessment in which it was shown that the estimated levelized CO₂ emissions avoidance costs span a wide range, between 85-534 €/tCO₂ avoided, depending on the size and location of the individual mill, and on the assumptions applied regarding the maturity of the capture technology, available transportation modes, energy prices, and heat integration scenario. It was also shown that the cost-optimal strategy for heat supply to drive the CO₂ capture process is highly context dependent. The electricity system, and more specifically, the electricity price and emissions intensity, has a large impact on the cost optimal heat supply strategy. If electricity prices and emissions intensity are low, sacrificing electricity production to supply heat for the capture process is a lower cost heat supply strategy than investing in additional boiler capacity and combusting biomass. However, if electricity prices are high, the opposite is true. For the sector as a whole, applying the cost-optimal heat supply scenario to each mill reduces the estimated avoidance cost for sector-wide CCS implementation by 3-4 % compared to applying the same heat supply strategy to all of the mills. Furthermore, the distance between the mill and a suitable harbor for CO₂ transport is shown to have a large effect on the total CO₂ avoidance cost, especially in a system where onshore pipelines are not available as a transport option. These results highlight the importance of accounting for regional factors when estimating the cost of CCS projects.

Generally, the mills with the lowest estimated costs for CDR are relatively large kraft pulp mills located along the coast in the southern parts of Sweden. Such mills could present interesting opportunities for early mover Bio-CCS projects, provided that the implementation of CO₂ capture at these mills is practically feasible.

7 REFERENCES

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A APPENDIX A

Table A.1 shows the mills included in this work, their yearly fossil and (estimated) biogenic emissions, and their location.

Table A.1. List of mills included in this work, including country where the mill is located and the yearly fossil and (estimated) biogenic CO₂ emissions.

Mill name	Country	Fossil CO ₂ [kt/a]	(Estimated) biogenic CO ₂ [kt/a]
Zellstoff Pöls Aktiengesellschaft	Austria	0	1140
AustroCel Hallein GmbH	Austria	0	381
Smurfit Kappa Nettingsdorf AG & Co KG	Austria	0	354
Mondi Frantschach GmbH	Austria	0	895
BURGO ARDENNES	Belgium	0	1070
STORA ENSO LANGERBRUGGE	Belgium	163	441
SVILOZA AD	Bulgaria	11	418
Stora Enso Oyj, Enocell Mill, Uimaharjun tehdas, Enocellin tehdas	Finland	58	1311
Stora Enso Oyj, Imatran tehtaas	Finland	182	2178
Metsä Fibre Oy, Joutsenon tehdas	Finland	28	1311
Metsä Fibre Oy Kemi, Puunjalostusteollisuus	Finland	68	1451
UPM-Kymmene Oyj, Kymi	Finland	78	1052
UPM-Kymmene Oyj, Kaukaan tehtaas	Finland	76	983
UPM Metsä Fibre Oy, Rauman tehdas	Finland	65	1304
Metsä Fibre Oy, Äänekosken biotuotetehtas	Finland	0	3100
STORA ENSO OULU OY, Oulun tehdas, Oulu	Finland	17	1173
Stora Enso Oyj, Varkauden tehtaas	Finland	42	625
FIBRE EXCELLENCE SAINT-GAUDENS	France	0	654
SMURFIT KAPPA CELLULOSE DU PIN	France	37	795
FIBRE EXCELLENCE PROVENCE	France	0	457
RAYONIER A.M. TARTAS	France	0	489
SYLVAMO	France	0	821
Mercer Stendal GmbH	Germany	0	1740
LEIPA Georg Leinfelder Werk Schwedt Süd	Germany	65	359
Schwarz Maxau GmbH	Germany	139	285
Europaec (CI) Viana DS Smith	Portugal	0	584
NAVIGATOR Setúbal (CI)	Portugal	0	1470
Navigator Pulp Cacia, S.A. (CI)	Portugal	0	794
Celulose Beira Industrial (Celbi), S.A. (CI)	Portugal	0	1060
Navigator Figueira (CI)	Portugal	0	1280
CEASA ENCE- FÁBRICA DE NAVIA	Spain	0	1370
SAICA PAPER EL BURGO DE EBRO	Spain	154	464
Skutskärs Bruk	Sweden	0	1279
Billerud Sweden AB Skärblacka Bruk	Sweden	21	800
Södra Cell Mönsterås	Sweden	8	1831
Södra Cell Mörrum	Sweden	12	1127

Nymölla bruk, Sylvamo	Sweden	0	746
Stora Enso Hylte Bruk AB, Sweden Timber	Sweden	3	282
Södra Cell Värö	Sweden	10	1809
Skoghalls Bruk	Sweden	53	996
Gruvöns bruk	Sweden	11	1438
Bäckhammars Bruk	Sweden	7	529
Ahlstrom Aspa Bruk AB	Sweden	12	394
Billerud Skog & Industri AB, Frövi, Rockhammar	Sweden	25	699
STORA ENSO FORS AB	Sweden	0	259
Korsnäsverket	Sweden	16	1183
Vallviks Bruk	Sweden	3	557
Iggesunds Bruk, Holmen	Sweden	14	974
SCA Östrands massafabrik	Sweden	79	1911
Mondi Dynäs AB	Sweden	17	617
Domsjö Fabriker AB	Sweden	2	430
Metsä Board Sverige AB, Husums fabr	Sweden	71	1418
SCA Obbola AB	Sweden	25	501
Billerud Karlsborgs bruk	Sweden	11	786
Smurfit Kappa Kraftliner Piteå	Sweden	10	1179
SCA Munksunds pappersbruk	Sweden	11	643
Caledonian Paper Mill	UK	15	302
Workington Board Mill EPR/BJ7590IB Iggesund	UK	0	531